

FINAL REPORT

ACTION WOWnature

INDEX

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. THE WOWNATURE ACTION PROJECT	5
The project in a nutshell	6
Issues addressed and project aims	6
Project phases and features and planned project deliverables	7
3. PROJECT AREAS	8
Bosco Limite	11
Bosco del Quarelo	12
Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon	12
4. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING	13
5. EXPERIMENT DESIGN	13
6. AIR MONITORING	15
Description of the sensors	15
Sensors' location	15
Wiseair analysis	17
Methodology	18
Results	24
Discussion of results	25
7. CITIZENS' CONTRIBUTION AND ENGAGEMENT	26
Who was involved	26
Citizens' inputs and support	27
Citizens' response	29
8. DISSEMINATION	32
9. ISSUES ENCOUNTERED	33
10. REFERENCES	33

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes the aims, design, implementation, and results of the **WOWNATURE project**, a project developed in the context of the **first ACTION open call**, i.e., a **call for citizen science projects related to pollution funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824603**. The project **aimed to measure the air pollution mitigation capacity of urban and peri-urban forests by using innovative sensors and by engaging citizens throughout the process** (i.e., experiment design, safekeeping of sensors, and dissemination of results) with the support of the WOWNature web-based platform, thus **strengthening the argument in their favour as an effective policy to tackle air pollution**.

The analyses performed on the data collected from three forests in the Po Valley found **statistical evidence that support the two hypotheses "air quality is better within the forest rather than outside the forest" and "the forest acts as a buffer, reducing the pollution from linear/punctiform sources of pollution"**.

The contents of this report reflect the author's views. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

1. INTRODUCTION

Etifor¹ is a spin-off company of the University of Padova whose work is driven by the company's mission: **to restore the balance between people and nature**. To fulfil this mission, Etifor's team works on multiple levels to help organizations, people, and forest managers to improve the planet around us with a responsible approach based on **science, innovation, and good governance**. Over the years, Etifor collaborated with private companies, civil society organizations, citizens, and public bodies to **improve the economic, environmental, and social benefits of policies, projects, and investments**².

In particular, Etifor established a long-lasting collaboration with the **Lowland Forestry Association (Associazione Forestale di Pianura, AFP)**³, an association which Etifor provides technical support to. **AFP groups several public and private forest owners** mainly located in the Po Valley – within the administrative boundaries of the Italian regions Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, and Lombardy – whose main objectives (relevant for this report) are to:

- facilitate access to funds, investments, and grants
- raise awareness on, and promote knowledge of, lowland forests and their importance
- value and promote the ecological, recreational, and educational use of lowland forests
- protect, enhance, and value the ecosystem services provided by lowland forests
- manage the forests in a responsible way, according to the Forest Stewardship Council® (FSC®) principles, criteria, and standards

Since 2019, AFP joined WOWnature® (www.wownature.eu), a web-based platform designed and created by Etifor connecting landowners, companies, associations, and citizens, creating an innovative public-private and multi-level partnership for tree planting finance and creation of new forest areas. Over the two years of activity, WOWnature expanded its community, a community that actively contributed to tens of projects of reforestation, forest restoration, or forest protection.

After many years of collaboration, both Etifor and AFP realized and agreed that **identifying, assessing, and communicating the benefits provided by forests are fundamental activities to raise awareness about their importance; and the increased awareness, in turn, can favour the fundraising needed for the creation of additional forests and their proper and responsible management**. These forests, in turn, directly and indirectly contribute to our wellbeing, providing a wide range of benefits: the so-called ecosystem services (BOX 1).

¹ <https://www.etifor.com/en/>

² <https://www.etifor.com/en/clients/>

³ <https://forestedipianura.it/>

BOX 1 ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

According to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005), which can be considered one of the main references on this topic, ecosystem services are defined as the “benefits people obtain from ecosystem”. The MA divides ecosystem services in four categories:

1. Provisioning services (that include, for instance, the provision of food, materials, or energy)
2. Regulating services (that include, for instance, purification of water or climate regulation)
3. Cultural services (that include, for instance, the use of natural ecosystems for outdoor activities, or as a source of inspiration in arts, etc.), and
4. Supporting services, a category of services that are at the basis of the services of the abovementioned three categories or, in other words, make it possible for ecosystem to continue providing services (this category includes, for instance, nutrient cycling and soil formation).

These services, in turn, directly and indirectly influence different dimensions of human wellbeing and, ultimately, freedom of choice.

The Po Valley – where most of the forests of AFP are located – is characterized by a very poor air quality: in fact, it is one of the most polluted areas in Europe. An increasing body of evidence, however, indicates that **trees and forests may be a nature-based solution to mitigate this problem. Indeed, trees and forests have the singular capacity to capture air pollutants and particulate matter (PM) and remove them from the air** (see for example: Nowak *et al.*, 2006).

However, **citizens are not always aware of this ecosystem service provided by forests; and AFP was having some difficulties in communicating it because of the lack of data at the local- and/or forest-site level.** To address these problems, the WOWNATURE project – described in the next sections – was designed and submitted to the first ACTION open call, i.e., a call for citizen science projects related to pollution funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824603.

2. THE WOWNATURE ACTION PROJECT

THE PROJECT IN A NUTSHELL

The project aimed to measure the air pollution mitigation capacity of urban and peri-urban forests by using innovative sensors and by engaging citizens throughout the process (i.e., experiment design, safekeeping of sensors, and dissemination of results) with the support of the WOWNature web-based platform, thus strengthening the argument in their favour as an effective policy to tackle air pollution.

ISSUES ADDRESSED AND PROJECT AIMS

The issues addressed and the overarching and specific project aims can be summarized as follows (Table 1):

ISSUES ADDRESSED	SPECIFIC OR OVERARCHING PROJECT AIMS
Lack of data on the forests' air pollution mitigation potential at the local- and/or forest-site level	Creation of forest-site level datasets and analyses on specific forests' mitigation capacity
Limited awareness on trees' ability to capture particulate matter (PM)	Education and awareness raising through dissemination of the results of the study
Lack of public funds to finance green infrastructure development	Increased awareness on trees' ability to capture particulate matter (see previous row) may increase the willingness to contribute to green infrastructure development (e.g., donations for tree planting by individuals, CSR investments by companies, etc.)
Air pollution and its consequences on human health	Increased funding for creation of new forests (see previous row), thanks to the trees' ability to capture PM, can help to mitigate air pollution and its consequences
Citizens are seldom included in the design of policies	The data produced with the support and inputs of citizens may be used as a scientific basis for the development of green infrastructures policies
Science is often a predominantly scientist-led process	Favour a more participatory, inclusive, citizen-led science-making by involving citizens throughout the process

Table 1 - Summary of the overarching and specific project aims

To perform the air monitoring, **Wiseair**⁴ – an innovative start-up based in Milan – was involved as a subcontractor. Wiseair's mission is to allow everyone in the world to breathe clean air. Wiseair's team believes that a problem that cannot be measured is a problem that cannot be addressed; thus, Wiseair's team works to **allow citizens, municipalities, and companies to measure air quality, creating actionable and solution-oriented data and information and raising awareness on the topic**. To do so, Wiseair developed **low-cost sensors** (called "Arianna", described in the next sections) that can be deployed in urban and natural areas; and they provide a full service of data analysis, data visualization, and support to decision-making.

PROJECT PHASES AND FEATURES AND PLANNED PROJECT DELIVERABLES

Once approved, the main phases of the project (described in detail in the next sections) consisted in:

- Identification of project areas
- Stakeholder mapping
- Experiment design
- Stakeholder engagement
- Placement of sensors
- Monitoring of the sensors and download of the data collected
- Data analysis
- Dissemination of results

As already mentioned in the introduction, the project was designed and submitted to the first ACTION open call, i.e., a call for citizen science projects related to pollution funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Thus, the **project explicitly aimed to involve citizens throughout its multiple phases** – bringing together citizens belonging to different groups and entities (e.g., public administrations, NGOs, associations, businesses, etc.) **and aligning research with their needs and values – in the belief that opening up research and innovation to society can help us in finding solutions to the most urgent challenges of our epoch.** Citizens' contribution and engagement is detailed in each relevant section and is summarized in Section 7.

Thanks to citizens' contributions and support, the project aimed to design and implement a **participatory 6-months air quality monitoring (and subsequent analysis) to assess the mitigation capacity of three specific forests.** The planned final results of the project consisted in the production of:

- a new air quality dataset at the site-level,
- a technical analysis to assess the mitigation capacity of the three forests included in the study,
- the production of a short video explaining the project, and
- a final report explaining both the project and the results of the analysis (i.e., this document).

3. PROJECT AREAS

As already mentioned in the introduction, **the Po Valley is a territory characterized by very poor air quality, with the concentration of several pollutants that often exceed the average target values indicated for protection of human health** (Figure 1 shows, as an example, PM2.5). Despite the application of the current European legislation devoted to air pollution control, it has been identified as one of the hot spot places where pollutant levels will remain problematic, with an estimated loss of ten months of life expectancy due to the high levels of fine particulate matter concentration⁵.

Figure 1 - PM2.5 Annual target value for the protection of human health. Source: European Environment Agency (EEA), downloaded from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/pm2.5-annual-target-value-4>

The three project sites were selected within the Po Valley, drawing from the forests of AFP. To select among the multiple forests of the association, the following criteria have been used:

- Proximity of pollution sources (e.g., large roads or highways)
- Presence of active groups of citizens with a stake on the forest
- Forest structure, age, shape, and size. In this case the aim was to obtain data from similar forests at different stages of growth, so that in case one or more of the younger forests did not show any effect on air pollution while the older(s) did, it would have been possible to estimate an approximate age at which this forest type starts having a measurable and significant effect on air pollution.

Based on these criteria, the most suitable forests identified – pinned in Figure 2 – were:

- ➔ **Bosco Limite**, located in Carmignano di Brenta (PD)

- ➔ **Bosco del Quarelo**, located in Vicenza (VI)

- ➔ **Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon**, located in San Stino di Livenza (VE)

Being all these forests certified according to the FSC responsible management standards, many data (about their physical characteristics, social and environmental resources, etc.) were already available and facilitated the development of the project. The full list of the forest managers whose forests were considered for the study is available at the WaldPlus' certificate page in the FSC international database⁶.

Figure 2 – The location of the three forests selected for the experiment.

THE FOREST STEWARDSHIP COUNCIL® (FSC®)

The Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) is an international non-profit, multistakeholder organization. Its mission is to “promote environmentally appropriate, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world’s forests” (<https://fsc.org/en/about-us>).

To accomplish this mission, FSC developed a voluntary certification scheme. This scheme “sets out best practices for forest management worldwide. By becoming FSC certified, forest owners and managers demonstrate that they are managing their forests responsibly. [...] All forest products can be certified, be it timber or non-timber forest products such as mushrooms and latex, but timber is the main product. [...] Additional to the forest management standard, there is a chain of custody standard to provide credible assurance that forest products sold as FSC certified originate from well-managed forests, controlled sources, reclaimed materials, or a mixture of these. FSC chain of custody certification facilitates the transparent flow of goods from the forest, through all the processing and trading stages, to the final consumer.” (FSC-RP-Standard Setting V1-1 - Standard Setting in FSC).

Moreover, as regards the benefits that people obtain from forests, it is worth mentioning that according to FSC “in FSC certified forests, valuable ecosystem services are also protected – and in 2018, FSC introduced a procedure to demonstrate and communicate about the positive impact of responsible forest management on ecosystem services. These verified positive impacts aim to facilitate payments for ecosystem services and provide access to other benefits, thereby adding business value for those who responsibly manage forests and those who take action to preserve forest ecosystem services” (<https://fsc.org/en/for-forests/ecosystem-services>).

BOSCO LIMITE

Bosco Limite is an 8-years-old forest that was planted in 2012 on a 2,6 hectares-wide land that was previously used for maize cultivation in Carmignano di Brenta (PD). Planted to increase the environmental, educational, and recreational functions of the area, the forest is also an innovative Forest Infiltration Area, i.e., a forest crisscrossed by channels to recharge the aquifer⁷.

The forest hosts more than 2,300 trees, whose species composition was selected to resemble and recreate the typical oak-hornbeam lowland forests of the Po Valley and, therefore, included species such as *Quercus robur*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Fraxinus ornus* and *angustifolia*, *Ulmus minor*, *Acer campestre*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Cornus sanguinea*, etc. Indeed, the Po Valley – that today is a territory with high levels of anthropogenic disturbance at the landscape level (Figure 3) – centuries ago would have shown thousands of hectares of such forests; today, almost all of the old forests have disappeared as a consequence of the deforestation and agricultural conversion carried out over centuries (mainly from XI and XX centuries).

The average height of trees, today, is about 6-7m with the highest trees that reach 10-14m. The forest is often used by local communities for recreational activities (walking, wild herbs and mushrooms picking, barbecue, etc.) and by the schools for educational activities. Starting from this autumn, Bosco Limite will also host a Forest kindergarten.

According to the data collected by the Regional Environmental Protection Agency station nearby, the total annual rainfall in the area in 2020 was equal to 850.8 mm, spread over a total of 81 days of rain; the main direction of the wind was North-East at an average speed of 1.2m/s⁸.

Fig. 4 Percentage of the Italian macro-regions occupied by the different land-use/land-cover classes. A = Alps; B = Apennines; C = Po river plain; D = coastal areas; E = Sicily; F = Sardinia

Figure 3 – Falucci (2006) analysis of land-use cover and land-use change for multiple Italian macro-regions 1960-2000. Areas of interest (Po river plain) is the one labelled with the letter C.

⁷ More information: <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/metadata/case-studies/bosco-limite-a-participatory-strategy-of-water-saving-and-aquifer-artificial-recharge-in-northern-italy>

⁸ Source: daily measurements from the “Grantorto” station in 2020 for rainfall (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0177_2020_PREC.htm), wind direction (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0177_2020_VDIREZ.htm) and wind speed (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0177_2020_VVENTO.htm)

BOSCO DEL QUARELO

Bosco del Quarelo is a forest that was planted in 2007 in Vicenza (VI) on land that was previously used for agricultural purposes. The forest is 9 hectares-wide and includes two main forest types: one part is similar to Bosco Limite, resembling the typical oak-hornbeam lowland forests of the Po Valley, another part includes more hygrophilous species where the main species are *Salix alba*, *Populus alba*, *Populus nigra*, *Salix cinerea*, *Salix triandra*, *Viburnum opulus*, *Frangula alnus*, *Corylus avellana*, etc. The forest also includes a humid area, very important for biodiversity.

The average height of trees, today, is about 8-10m with the highest trees that reach 16-18m. The forest is often used by local communities for recreational and sport activities (including fishing) and, since 2013, WWF Vicenza-Padova oversees fauna monitoring.

According to the data collected by the Regional Environmental Protection Agency station nearby, the total annual rainfall in the area in 2020 was equal to 987.6 mm, spread over a total of 88 days of rain; the main direction of the wind was East at an average speed of 0.8m/s⁹.

BOSCHI DI BANDIZIOL E PRASSACCON

Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon (i.e., Bandiziol and Prassaccon forests) were planted between 1995 and 1999 over a 120 hectares-wide area. Not all the area is forested – it also includes some lawns (equipped with a birdwatching tower) and a humid area. Even in this case, the idea was to resemble and recreate the typical oak-hornbeam lowland forests of the Po Valley, therefore the species composition of the forest is similar to those of Bosco Limite and Bosco del Quarelo. Today, the average height of trees, today, is about 8-12m with the highest trees that reach 18-20m.

The local population of San Stino di Livenza and surroundings is very attached to its forests. Indeed, many different groups of citizens use it for the most diverse purposes: sport (biking, horse riding, etc.), environmental education, recreation (e.g., birdwatching, fauna observation). In order to facilitate the coordination of different uses of the forests, a participative process to plan its management is going on since some years. During an open event¹⁰, the population agreed that assessing and valuing the ecosystem services provided by their forests was something desirable to support them and favour their responsible management.

According to the data collected by the Regional Environmental Protection Agency station nearby, the total annual rainfall in the area in 2020 was equal to 984.6 mm, spread over a total of 93 days of rain; the main direction of the wind was North-East at an average speed of 1.2m/s¹¹.

⁹ Source: daily measurements from the "Vicenza – Sant'Agostino" station in 2020 for rainfall (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0451_2020_PREC.htm), wind direction (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0451_2020_VDIREZ.htm), and wind speed (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0451_2020_VVENTO.htm)

¹⁰ <https://www.sanstino.it/index.php?area=21&menu=375&page=499&idnotizia=934&lingua=4>

¹¹ Source: daily measurements from the "Ponte di Piave" station in 2020 for rainfall (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0204_2020_PREC.htm), wind direction (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0204_2020_VDIREZ.htm), and wind speed (https://www.arpa.veneto.it/bollettini/storico/2020/0204_2020_VVENTO.htm)

4. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

After identifying the three project areas, Etifor conducted a stakeholder mapping. This was done going through the FSC certification documents and the documents of the several activities carried out in the past that included those forests. In the case of Bandiziol and Prassaccon forests, reference was made in particular to the participants of the abovementioned open event. The mapping was also enlarged with specific phone calls to the forest managers (i.e., Vicenza Municipality for Bosco del Quarelo, Azienda Agricola Moresco Adelia for Bosco Limite).

This mapping allowed to identify 11 groups/entities to be engaged with. Sadly, in the meanwhile, the Covid-19 started spreading, and Italy was initially hit very hard by the outbreak. All these activities had to be carried out during a period of strict lockdown and, therefore, impeded in person meetings. However, 10 of the groups identified confirmed their support to the project and gave their availability for one or more of its phases (i.e., air monitoring, dissemination of results, etc.). These stakeholders identified and engaged with were characterized by a discrete degree of diversity: they included municipalities, an agricultural enterprise, environmental NGOs, other associations.

5. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

The experiment design started before the engagement of the stakeholders, with a dialogue (both via email and in person in Berlin, during the kick-off meeting of the project) with the mentor assigned by the ACTION network and with Wiseair staff (mainly remotely at this stage). During this phase, the basic setup of the experiment was defined, including the number of sensors to be placed and their approximate location. Precautions were taken to account for possible risks (e.g., vandalism, malfunctioning of the sensors, etc.), which concretized in particular in placing a number of sensors higher than the number needed (i.e., redundancies were created). With the number and (approximate) location of sensors suggested by Wiseair and double-checked by the ACTION mentor, both the mentor and Wiseair confirmed that the experiment should have been able to provide significant results.

The experiment design did not stop here. After a lag period due to the Covid-19 outbreak, in September 2019, the moment to place the sensors arrived. Fortunately, at that moment it was possible to meet in person, provided the respect of safety measures. Therefore, the stakeholders were invited to install the sensors together with Etifor and Wiseair staff. People were introduced again to the project, and a recap was made to remind the importance of the study, the rationale behind the experiment, and the support needed from them (Figure 4). After this recap, the volunteers directly contributed to the experiment design by providing valuable information (based on their deep knowledge of the forest) about the safest places where to place the sensors to reduce the risk of vandalism and providing feedbacks and suggesting modifications to the (approximate) location initially proposed.

Figure 4 - explaining the project to the volunteers in Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon

14 Figure 5 - citizens contributed to the experiment design by indicating the most suitable locations for the sensors

6. AIR MONITORING

As already mentioned in the introduction, the 6-months monitoring service was subcontracted to Wiseair, an innovative start-up based in Milan aiming to unite people, municipalities, and companies in the defence of clean air. Starting from the belief that “a problem you cannot measure is a problem you cannot solve”, Wiseair specialized in data collection and data analysis with the ultimate goal of creating actionable and solution-oriented information, as well as raising awareness.

DESCRIPTION OF THE SENSORS

The experiment was conducted by using the “Arianna” devices as a primary source of data. The Arianna devices are sensors engineered and produced by Wiseair that can make hourly measurement of:

- particulate matter (specifically PM10, PM4, PM2.5, PM1)
- temperature
- humidity

The Arianna devices use the laser-scattering SPS30 sensor to measure particulate matter. This is a state-of-the-art sensor produced by the Swiss company Sensirion, one of the leaders in the sector of sensor technology. The sensor SPS30 is calibrated directly in the factory and has an autocleaning system that prevents the worsening of the quality of the measurements over time.

The sensor SPS30 is the only low-cost sensor available on the market that achieved the MCERTS certification¹², a certification that ensures the high-quality of the data collected.

SENSORS' LOCATION

7 sensors were placed in each project area (Bosco Limite, Bosco del Quarelo, Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon, see Section 3), **for a total of 21 sensors**. The number of sensors that were placed was higher than the number needed to carry out the analysis (i.e., redundancies were intentionally planned, 5 sensors would have been sufficient) in order to prevent possible problems from malfunctioning, vandalism, or other problems of one or more of the sensors.

The sensors were located well within the forests and at their edges, so that it was possible to test the two hypotheses of the experiment:

- 1. Air quality is better within the forest rather than outside the forest**
- 2. The forest acts as a buffer, reducing the pollution from linear/punctiform sources of pollution**

The location of the sensors – that was defined with the support of the citizens' groups supporting the project, based in their deep knowledge of the forests – is represented in the figures below (Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8). All sensors were placed approximately at the same height (ranging from 1.6 and 2 meters).

¹² <https://www.sensirion.com/en/about-us/newsroom/news-and-press-releases/detail/news/first-mass-market-particulate-matter-sensor-awarded-with-mcerts-certification/>

Figure 6 – Location of the sensors in Bosco Limite (Carmignano di Brenta, PD)

Figure 7 - Location of the sensors in Bosco del Quarelo (Vicenza, VI)

Figure 7 - Location of the sensors in Boschi Bandiziol e Prassaccon (San Stino di Livenza, VE)

WISEAIR ANALYSIS

As already mentioned in the last section, the analysis aimed to test the following hypotheses:

1. Air quality is better within the forest rather than outside the forest
2. The forest acts as a buffer, reducing the pollution from linear/punctiform sources of pollution

The following paragraphs provide a summary of the analysis conducted, focusing in particular on methodology and results. Further and more detailed information can be found in the technical report prepared by Wiseair (Italian only)¹³.

METHODOLOGY

Two different analyses were conducted to validate the two hypotheses. In both cases, the data collected by the sensors are improved thanks to the adoption of corrective models based on inputs from multiple sources (official data from regional monitoring stations, historical data from the sensors, meteorological conditions, etc.).

In particular, in order to increase the reliability and precision of the analysis, the data collected have been re-elaborated by:

- Extracting the hourly average of the measurements to level them out and make them comparable
- Applying two algorithms (one proposed by Sreibl and one developed by Wiseair), needed because laser-scattering sensors are sensitive to relative humidity
- Applying a median filter on a 3-hours timeframe to remove the outliers

To check whether the effects of the forests are statistically significant for Hypothesis 1 and 2, in both cases **the paired t-test was performed**.

.....

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED TO TEST HYPOTHESIS 1

As regards Hypothesis 1 (“air quality is better within the forest rather than outside the forest”), the values registered by the sensors at the edges of the forests were compared to the values registered by the sensors deep in the forests (represented respectively in orange and green in the maps below) (Figure 9, Figure 10, and Figure 11).

Figure 9 - representation of sensors “at the edges of the forest” (orange) and “deep in the forest” (green) in Bosco Limite

Figure 10 – representation of sensors “at the edges of the forest” (orange) and “deep in the forest” (green) in Bosco del Quarelo

Figure 11 – representation of sensors “at the edges of the forest” (orange) and “deep in the forest” (green) in Boschi Bandiziol e Prassaccon

After the corrections explained in Section 6.3.1, the daily average for measurements at the edges and in the deep of the forests were extracted. The analysis focused on PM_{2.5} because the sensors can measure this pollutant with a high accuracy and because national and international norms prescribe limits of concentration that facilitate the interpretation of results. The graphs below (Graph 1, Graph 2, and Graph 3) show the time series obtained by comparing the two average values over time.

19 **Graph 1** – Bosco Limite: PM_{2.5} daily average (µg/m³) in the deep (blue line) and at the edges (orange line) of the forest.

Graph 2 – Bosco del Quarelo: PM2.5 daily average (µg/m³) in the deep (blue line) and at the edges (orange line) of the forest.

Graph 3 – Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon: PM2.5 daily average (µg/m³) in the deep (blue line) and at the edges (orange line) of the forest.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED TO TEST HYPOTHESIS 2

To test Hypothesis 2 (“the forest acts as a buffer, reducing the pollution from linear/punctiform sources of pollution”), the sensors of each forest were labelled as “protected” or “exposed”, i.e., having (orange in the map below) or not having (green in the map below) a line of sight on the source of pollution (Figure 12, Figure 13, and Figure 14).

Figure 12 – The sensors in Bosco Limite: the orange ones are “exposed”, while the green ones are “protected”

Figure 13 – The sensors in Bosco del Quarelo: the orange ones are “exposed”, while the green ones are “protected”

Figure 14 – The sensors in Bosco di Bandiziol e Prassaccon: the orange ones are “exposed”, while the green ones are “protected”

The sources of pollution considered are:

- Road transport (i.e., highways or highly frequented roads), categorized as Macrosector 7 in emission inventories
- Industrial or not industrial buildings where combustion happens, categorized as Macrosectors 1, 2, 3, and 4

because these sectors are responsible for more than 84% of the emissions of PM10 inventoried by ISPRA (Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research) in the provinces of Vicenza and Venezia.

After the corrections explained in Section 6.3.1, the daily average for measurements of “exposed” and “protected” sensors were extracted. The analysis focused on PM2.5 for the same reasons as for Hypothesis 1. The graphs below show the time series obtained by comparing the two average values over time (Graph 4, Graph 5, and Graph 6).

Graph 4 – Bosco Limite: PM2.5 daily average ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for “protected” (blue) and “exposed” (orange) sensors

Graph 5 – Bosco del Quarelo: PM2.5 daily average ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for “protected” (blue) and “exposed” (orange) sensors

Graph 6 – Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon: PM2.5 daily average ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for “protected” (blue) and “exposed” (orange) sensors

RESULTS

The datasets – resulting from a maximum of 7 sensors to a minimum of no less than 4 sensors per forest for the whole monitoring period – have been made publicly available on Zenodo . Starting from these datasets, the analysis performed and validated with the paired t-test allowed to verify the two hypotheses. The results of the analysis can be summarized as follows:

Hypothesis 1: air quality is better within the forest rather than outside the forest:

- Bosco Limite: there is statistically significant evidence in terms of air quality within and outside the forest that supports to the hypothesis with a possibility of being wrong equal to 0.01% (almost null)
- Bosco del Quarelo: there is no statistically significant evidence in terms of air quality within and outside the forest that supports to the hypothesis. This result is unexpected; further research would be needed to explain it
- Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon: there is statistically significant evidence in terms of air quality within and outside the forest that supports to the hypothesis with a possibility of being wrong equal to 11%

Hypothesis 2: the forest acts as a buffer, reducing the pollution from linear/punctiform sources of pollution:

- Bosco Limite: there is statistically significant evidence that the protected sensors recorded lower values of pollutants than the exposed ones. This supports the hypothesis with a possibility of being wrong equal to 0.01% (almost null)
- Bosco del Quarelo: there is statistical evidence that the exposed sensors recorded lower values of pollutants than the protected ones. This result is unexpected; further research would be needed to explain it. However, further analysis carried out that considers additional sources of pollution allow to affirm that the forest does, in fact, act as a buffer.
- Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon: there is no statistically significant evidence that the protected sensors recorded lower values of pollutants than the exposed ones. This result is unexpected; further research would be needed to explain it

The results of the analysis are summarized in Table 2.

FOREST	HYPOTHESIS 1	HYPOTHESIS 2
Bosco Limite	CONFIRMED	CONFIRMED
Bosco del Quarelo	NOT CONFIRMED	CONFIRMED (with additional analysis)
Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon	CONFIRMED	NOT CONFIRMED

Table 2 – Summary of the results of the analysis

Discussion of results

Many variables influence these effects: canopy size, leaf size, and leaf structure are all variables that play a role. Moreover, the extent to which a given patch of forest performs this filtering activity may also depend on the physical structure of the surrounding land as well as on the wind direction and location of sources of pollution (that may favour the dispersion of PM or not).

However, **the results of the analysis at the local level are consistent with the available body of evidence, i.e., trees do have a positive effect on air quality.** In the context of this specific project – which is a citizen science project and, as such, aims to be aligned with citizens’ values and interests – is a very positive result. Indeed, many volunteers reported that “the willingness to verify the positive impacts of trees on air pollution” and “the willingness to contribute to scientific research on ecological utility of forests” were among the main motivations to participate¹⁵.

Further research may include a specific valuation to quantify the exact amount of PM removal by single forests (e.g., X kg of PM2.5 per year). Indeed, this kind of analysis may be interesting for companies willing to reach “net zero pollution targets”, applying strategies and reasonings similar to “net zero emissions” strategies that some companies already apply, for instance, to CO2 emissions.

7. CITIZENS' CONTRIBUTION AND ENGAGEMENT

This section and its subsections summarize the citizens' contribution and engagement, that was only partially mentioned in different parts of the document.

WHO WAS INVOLVED

As already mentioned in Section 4, the stakeholder mapping allowed to identify 11 groups/entities to be engaged with. All except one confirmed their support to the project and gave their availability for one or more of its phases (Table 3), adding up to the efforts of Etifor and Wiseair.

NAME	DESCRIPTION	FOREST OF INTEREST	ROLE: SUPPORTING...
Associazione Forestale di Pianura (AFP)	Association that groups public and private forest owners to support responsible forest management and improvement of forests	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder mapping and engagement Experiment design Dissemination of results
FSC Italia	No-profit organization aligned with the objectives of FSC International promoting responsible forest management	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Placement of sensors Monthly download of the data collected Dissemination of results
Comune di San Stino di Livenza	Local municipality. Owner and manager of Bosco del Quarelo.	Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder mapping and engagement Experiment design Dissemination of results
Associazione Il Bosco di S. Stino	Nature conservation association entrusted with some activities in Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon (mainly related to education and nature conservation)	Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Placement of sensors Monthly download of the data collected Dissemination of results
Ass. Naturalistica Sandonatese	Nature conservation association committed to environmental education and research	Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Dissemination of results
Legambiente Veneto Orientale	Local nature conservation association committed to environmental protection and awareness raising	Boschi di Bandiziol e Prassaccon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Dissemination of results
Azienda Agricola Moresco Adelia	Agricultural enterprise. Owner and manager of Bosco Limite. Regularly organizing and/or supporting guided visits to the forest.	Bosco Limite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Placement of sensors Monthly download of the data collected Dissemination of results
Raise	Association carrying out Kindergarden activities in Bosco Limite	Bosco Limite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of results
Comune di Vicenza	Local municipality. Owner and manager of Bosco del Quarelo.	Bosco del Quarelo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder mapping and engagement Experiment design Dissemination of results
WWF Vicenza - Padova	Local nature conservation association. Supports Comune di Vicenza with some activities related to: environmental education, biodiversity monitoring, management for recreational purposes.	Bosco del Quarelo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Placement of sensors Monthly download of the data collected Dissemination of results

CITIZENS' INPUTS AND SUPPORT

Citizens provided valuable support in the following phases:

- ➔ Identification of the most suitable location for the sensors (Figure 15)
- ➔ Placement of the sensors (Figure 16)
- ➔ Monitoring and, in case of damages to the sensors, warning (Figure 17)
- ➔ Monthly download of the data collected (Figure 18)
- ➔ Dissemination (Figure 19)

Figure 15 – citizens supported the identification of the most appropriate location for each sensor

Figure 16 – citizens supported the placement of the sensors

Figure 17 – citizens constantly monitored the sensors and promptly warned about damages, if any. This photo was taken by a volunteer in Boschi Bandiziol e Prassaccon and shows a sensor that was vandalized by unknowns.

Figure 18 – A volunteer of one of the organizations (FSC Italia) supporting the project carries out one of the monthly download of the data collected by the sensors.

Figure 19 – Raise (the association that uses Bosco Limite for running a Kindergarden), shares the results of the study, supporting the dissemination phase, on its social media profile.

CITIZENS' RESPONSE

The basic idea behind the implantation and dissemination of the project was to engage with a limited number of very committed and passionate people (i.e., the citizens belonging to the organizations having a stake or carrying out activities in the forests) during the more “practical” phases of the project and then taking advantage of their networks to disseminate its results to a wider public. The monitoring survey conducted at the end of the project demonstrated the successful implementation of this strategy. Indeed, participants that filled in the survey (not all of them filled it in) reported that:

- Participating in the project was an opportunity to do something important (Figure 20), useful (Figure 21), and a good thing to do (Figure 22)
- The decision to participate was driven by the willingness to support scientific research (Figure 23) on topics of personal interest (Figure 24) and by the belief that the project could help to value forests (Figure 25)
- All of them would contribute to the dissemination of results (Figure 26)

29 **Figure 20** – volunteers reported that participating in the project was an opportunity to do something important

Figure 21 – volunteers reported that participating in the project was an opportunity to do something useful

Figure 22 – volunteers reported that participating in the project was a good thing to do

Figure 23 – volunteers reported that the decision to participate was driven by the willingness to support scientific research

😊 Quanto sei interessato al tema dei benefici forniti dalle foreste e, in particolare, alla loro capacità di miglioramento della qualità dell'aria?

Figure 24 – the ability of forests to mitigate air quality is a topic of personal interest for the volunteers

🗳️ Hai deciso di partecipare al progetto perché pensi che i risultati del progetto possano contribuire alla valorizzazione delle foreste?

Figure 25 – volunteers believe that the results of the project can support the valorisation of forests

🗳️ Pensi che contribuirai alla diffusione dei risultati dello studio?

Figure 26 – all the participants to the survey declared that they would contribute to the dissemination of results

8. DISSEMINATION

For the dissemination of results, a short video explaining the project was produced by Etifor and published on WOWnature social media together with the link to an article on WOWnature blog¹⁷. From here it was possible to download the short version of the report¹⁸, which included an external link to the detailed analysis¹⁹. The associations and citizens' groups that participated in the experiment were mentioned and invited to share the post, taking advantage of their network for further disseminating the results. Furthermore, the project was also advertised in one of Etifor's newsletters, which have a different audience with respect to WOWnature's one. This document can be also published on Etifor website, on the project's webpage.

Table 4 summarizes the **preliminary results of the dissemination** (as of 06/08/2021), achieved thanks to the valuable support provided by the citizens' groups that shared and forwarded the video, article, and reports:

ACTIVITY/CHANNEL OF DISSEMINATION	RESULTS
Video on social media	3381 views 11 shares 5725 people reached 61 reactions 780 click on the post
Article on WOWnature blog	120 unique visits
Newsletter Etifor	3738 contacts reached 1009 contacts opened the newsletter

Table 4 – Summary of the results of the dissemination (as of 06/08/2021)

However, the dissemination will never really end. Indeed, the idea of the project was to gather data and evidence about the benefits provided by forests with the specific aim to support the argument in their favour as a nature-based solution able to tackle the problem of air pollution. Thus, the results of this projects will be used when speaking with potential investors (companies willing to implement CSR strategies, etc.) to motivate them in finalizing the investment: a process that can be considered dissemination. Furthermore, one of the associations supporting the project reported that “the results of the study are really interesting and provide us with an additional argument in support of the activities we are carrying out within the forest, we may use this information when we speak with potential users of our service”²⁰.

¹⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/827884420715302/videos/2869359573276631>

¹⁷ https://www.wownature.eu/mitigazione-inquinamento-foreste/?fbclid=IwAR1BoIFkY9XuBY50zNbXMStnuwm2H-LsQi7EpgbTXDXW_-MCEybVYQ-DV3g

¹⁸ https://www.wownature.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/WISEAIR_ETIFOR_report_compressed.pdf

¹⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZEgw44TqSynN_ClyEa_xYBwGjBGXH43qbGYgA2AEnO/edit

²⁰ Source: personal communication (June 2021). Translated from Italian.

9. ISSUES ENCOUNTERED

Some issues were encountered during the different phases of the project. In particular:

- Covid-19 pandemic outbreak – as already mentioned in previous sections, Italy was hit very hard by the first outbreak of Covid-19. In the first phases of the project, all the activities had to be carried out during a period of strict lockdown and, therefore, impeded in person meetings. This, in turn, had at least two consequences:
 - o Increased difficulty in reaching out to, and keep engagement with, certain stakeholders (single citizens or groups of citizens), in particular those who are less confident with videocalls, emails, and technology in general;
 - o Increased difficulty in building trust, which is, in our opinion, a key aspect for any project involving local communities.
- Vandalism – the sensors were located in forests that are open to the public (not fenced or restricted in any way, not under video surveillance, etc.) and highly popular. During the period of monitoring, some sensors were damaged and/or stolen by unknowns. This issue was, to a certain extent, expected. Therefore, the following precautions were taken:
 - o The experiment was designed with planned redundancies (i.e., more sensors than the minimum number needed were placed), so that if any of them was stolen or damaged the experiment would have not been compromised
 - o The sensors were “hidden” in not-so-popular parts of the forest when possible. On the one hand, this strategy limited the dissemination potential of the project (e.g., other people interested in air quality and/or forests may have started to follow and/or support the project) but, on the other hand, letting the sensors in visible places would have increased the risk of vandalism even further, maybe up to a point where the experiment could have been fully compromised.
- Sensitivity to humidity – the low-cost sensors are sensitive to humidity. This issue can be partially addressed when processing data but cannot be fully eliminated. Thus, the quality of the data collected in extremely humid days (>95%) is lower than usual. This condition may have influenced the measurement made in Boschi Bandiziol e Prassaccon, the most difficult ones to explain.

10. REFERENCES

- Falcucci, A., Maiorano, L., Boitani, L. “Changes in Land-Use/Land-Cover Patterns in Italy and Their Implications for Biodiversity Conservation.” *Landscape Ecology* 22 (March 27, 2006): 617–31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-006-9056-4>
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005). *Ecosystems and human well-being*. Washington, D.C: Island Press.
- Nowak, D.J., Crane, D. E., & Stevens, J. C. (2006). Air pollution removal by urban trees and shrubs in the United States. *Urban forestry & urban greening*, 4(3-4), 115-123.